

Conservation and the Distribution of a Defining Property(energy/momentum) Versus The Distribution of Probability

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In classical statistical mechanics, e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas, one tries to find the probability distribution of a particular quantity such as particle energy $pp/2m$. Thus there is a distribution in a quantity, making it the stochastic variable. This quantity, however, is subject to a conservation law i.e. elastic two particle scattering.

In a previous note (1), we considered the case of reflection/refraction and called momentum the stochastic variable and noted that it too was linked with conservation. In fact, we argued that both the MB gas and reflection/refraction followed the same stochastic law: $P(\text{variable } 1) P(\text{variable } 2) = P(\text{variable } 1 + \text{variable } 2)$ whether variable 1 is a scalar or vector. In (2), however, we noted that $\exp(ipx)$, a free particle wavefunction, treats p as a parameter with x being the "probability" variable.

This seems a little unusual because p , which is normally a variable in an MB gas and even in a quantum bound state i.e. $a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ takes on the role of a parameter i.e. $p=\hbar/\text{wavelength}$. Why this duality? Why is p a parameter for "x" of the probability distribution and yet at the same time a variable associated with conservation of momentum?

In this note, we argue that unlike the distribution of a defining property of a particle such as momentum or energy, one may have a distribution associated with probability itself. This we argue is the case for a reflection/refraction problem which applies to both light and a particle. In the case of light, there is an interface of two media with different indices of refraction and in the case of a particle an interface with two constant potentials. In both cases, total energy of the photon/particle is constant, but there are two choices or probabilities, reflection or refraction, but they are linked with different times. A single photon or particle can only undergo one at a time. One knows exactly the two values of momentum, but the probability of each is unknown. Thus unlike an MB gas where energy/momentum is being redistributed because the two particles of the outcome exist at the same time, here a probability of 1 must somehow be distributed to the two events..

Given that the incident momentum is p , the reflected $-p$ and the refracted p_2 , only considering a specific time event i.e. reflection or refraction, does not conserve momentum. In the MB case, a single time event i.e. scattering conserves both momentum and energy. Thus it seems that one does not deal with events in time. There is a distribution of probability in such a way as to ensure conservation of momentum, but does this probability already exist or get created at the interface point? We argued in (3) that if the scenario were deterministic one would have to follow it in time and treat each event separately. Rather we suggest that a distribution of probabilities allows for conservation of momentum, but this means that all three momenta exist at the interface x point as one is not considering an event at a precise point in time. This then allows for each momentum to have its own x distribution based on momentum p so that one may impose conservation of momentum and not have a deterministic time associated with the interface point.. This last idea of conservation of momentum appearing is not discussed in (3)

and allows for p to behave like a parameter for x while at the same time being a variable which is conserved.

In short, in an MB gas one distributes energy between two colliding particles in order to conserve total energy while for a quantum particle or photon which reflects/refracts one distributes probability to the two scenarios (reflection or refraction) such that momentum is conserved. Thus the nature of what is “distributed” is very different.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be calculated by imposing conservation i.e. elastic two body scattering and equal probabilities for a reaction and its time-reversed form. Then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

It may be immediately noted that the solution is $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ and that $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_l + e_k$. Furthermore the parameter “ k ” T has the same units as e_i and has the same physical sense (Temperature). Basically, one changes the energy distribution from e_1, e_2 to e_3, e_4 subject to conservation. One has two particles and at a given instant in time (Newtonian determinism) one shifts the energies (and corresponding momenta). ((1a)) and ((1b)) are equivalent to:

$$f(e_i + e_j) = f(e_i)f(e_j) \quad ((2))$$

One may note that physically one has an AND situation as shown specifically in ((1a)) and ((1b)). Thus one considers the product probabilities of e_1, e_2 together with e_3, e_4 together. This is why we call ((1a)), ((1b)) a distribution of energy.

As will be seen in the next section, it is possible to have ((2)) and not have an outcome situation at an instant in time - in other words one may break Newtonian determinism. This occurs when there are different outcome options which should exist at different times according to Newtonian determinism. In the MB gas, e_1, e_2 exist at t just before the collision and e_3, e_4 just after. E_3 and e_4 exist at the same time. Thus there is no difference in time of the outcomes. One need only consider probabilities of e_3, e_4 versus e_5, e_6 with $e_3 + e_4 = e_5 + e_6$. Thus MB statistics, even though involving probabilities, are completely consistent with Newtonian determinism. We argue that not all probabilistic situations, however, are. One may only distribute a variable (e.g. energy) if the two recipients (particle 1) and particle 2 exist at the same time. What if there is only one particle and two possible outcomes (with probabilities) which imply different times, yet one wants to impose the conservation of a variable associated with the different outcomes?

Reflection/Refraction

Reflection/refraction implies there are two possible exclusive outcomes for a photon reaching the interface of two media with different indices of refraction. This is somewhat like tossing a

coin, yet the probability of heads/tails is .5. Why is it not .5 for reflection/refraction? We suggest that a conservation law, namely that of momentum, is at work and so probability has to be “distributed” between the possible events to ensure a kind of average momentum conservation appears. A deterministic specific event i.e. a photon refracting links an incident photon to a reflected one which seems to imply conservation of momentum for this event and a different one for reflection. This would then not be linked to distributing probability to ensure conservation of momentum. The problem is that the two scenarios (incident photon - reflected photon) and (incident photon - refracted photon) represent events at different times in a deterministic picture. As argued in (3) if one wishes to consider all three events together, one must remove time i.e. determinism $x=p/m t$. This leads to a distribution in x so that the incident photon does not arrive at the interface at a specific time, but is rather associated with a probability distribution. What governs this distribution function? We argue one must have conservation of average momentum overall (average momentum) and so the x probability distribution is related to momentum p . Thus, p is like a parameter e.g. $1/\text{Temperature}$, but at the same time is a variable because it is conserved. As a variable it follows the same statistical rule as distributed energy in an MB gas i.e.

$$\text{Probability}(\text{variable } 1) \text{Probability}(\text{variable } 2) = \text{Probability}(\text{variable } 1 + \text{variable } 2) \quad ((3))$$

Why is this the case? We argue that classically momenta add and so one cannot distinguish between separate momenta and the sum. ((3)) means that the probability for p_1, p_2 in one dimension is the same as for p_3, p_4 if $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$.

((3)), however, is only part of the picture because one could in one dimension $\exp(ipb)$ where b is a constant which would mean no “ x ” distribution. “ l ” appears because one cannot exclude high p values i.e there is no drop-off as one deals with a constant p .

Thus one chooses p as the “probability” variable in ((3)) and replaces b with x to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ with p behaving as the parameter $p=h\bar{c}/\text{wavelength}$ while at the same time ((3)) ensures that there is the idea of conservation of momentum at work. In such a case, a single x value is used in ((3)) and so it is like a dummy parameter, but it becomes a probability distribution variable as one changes its value.

In fact, $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ are orthogonal functions which enhances the idea of momentum conservation. As a result, a photon or quantum particle with constant speed and momentum seems to be deterministic i.e. $x=p/m t$, but really there are discrete probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$ which create the statistical object $\exp(ipx)$. This allows for a distribution of probabilities by eliminating time (within a wavelength although $x=p/m t$ still holds on average) and considering the options together (as if they were at the same time, but only $\exp(ipx)$ s are present.

This approach applies to reflection/refraction which keeps momentum on average conserved and to two slit interference where the slit wall may shift the angle of the momentum through one slit and the other differently. Thus one does not have to enforce conservation of momentum, but may simply consider the “interference” of the x probability distributions. Again the two slit interference problem is one of distributing probability i.e. one considers the photon or particle going through both slits because time is removed due to the distribution $\exp(ipx)$ which means that one does not really have deterministic motion within the wavelength.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although both two body elastic scattering in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and reflection/refraction of light (or a quantum particle) such that total energy of the particle/photon is constant follow the same statistical form: $\text{Probability}(\text{variable 1}) \text{Probability}(\text{variable 2}) = \text{Probability}(\text{variable 1} + \text{variable 2})$ ((B)) where variable 1 is energy for the MB gas and momentum for the reflection/refraction problem and this law is linked to conservation of the variable i.e. there exists the same probability for any two values of variable 1 and 2 such that their sum is the same, there seems to be an important difference. This difference, we argue, is related to Newtonian determinism. In the case of an MB gas, the two final particles have their “new” energies e_3, e_4 at the same time. (The incident situation was e_1, e_2). Thus this is a distribution of energy problem consistent with Newtonian determinism because there is a specific single time for the outcome events i.e. the two particles.

On the other hand, one may consider a reflection/refraction problem. One might suggest that momentum, the variable in the problem, also is conserved and try to use ((B)). The problem is that the two events, reflection and refraction, are separated in time. A photon/ particle either reflects or refracts and the momentum of each is fixed i.e. $-p$ and p_2 . Thus there is not a distribution of momentum. Furthermore energy is constant so it is not distributed. What is distributed then? We argue that it is the probability for reflection and refraction. These, however, exist at different times, but like in the MB case, one would like to bring them “together”. This may be done by breaking Newtonian determinism. Thus the form $\exp(ipb)$ from ((B)) with b a constant and “ i ” used because all p values are acceptable, must change a little. In order to break the deterministic $x = p/m t$, one may drop time and use a probability distribution in x i.e. change $\exp(ipb)$ to $\exp(ipx)$. Thus p is like a variable in $\exp(ipb)$, but now plays the role of a parameter, like $1/\text{Temperature}$, in $\exp(ipx)$. With the removal of the exact time of an interaction due to probability, one may “distribute” probabilities to reflection and refraction in the same equations i.e. uses $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$ and $Ap - pB = Cp_2$ at $x=0$. This allows for a balance of average momentum by distributing the probabilities B, C (reflected, refracted) in terms of an incident weight A (which one may choose).

References

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